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Victim-Oriented Humanistic Policing as a New Model in Improving Services for Victims of Sexual Violent Crimes: Comparative Study of Indonesian Police, Japanese, and New Zealand

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Abstract

This research aims to examine service models for victims of sexual violent crimes in three countries, namely Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand. The research uses a descriptive-qualitative approach. The method used is case study comparison to then produce a new theoretical model related to victim-oriented humanistic policing (VOHP) for adaptation in Indonesia. Based on the identification and interpretation of research data using the Hoefnagels (1969) criminal policy analysis framework and Paterson's (2022) victim-oriented policing policy analysis, five new theoretical approaches were found regarding VOHP services for victims of sexual violent crimes in Indonesia. The five approaches include sustainable mentoring, practical interview skills, advocacy support, technology mastery, and strategic partnerships. These five new concepts emphasize a focus on institutional and cultural transformation of the National Police to prevent revictimization when dealing with victims. These five models are elaborations of models that have generally been applied universally, especially in Japan and New Zealand. It is hoped that this VOHP model can become the basis for better services for victims of sexual violent crimes in Indonesia.

Keywords: Sexual Violent Crimes, Crime Victim Services, National Police, Victim-Oriented Humanistic Policing

1. Introduction

Cases of sexual violent crimes in the world continue to increase from year to year. The victims of these two types of crime are predominantly women and children. However, quite a few men also experience similar cases,

although they are often ignored (Ashila and Barus, 2021). The 2021 World Health Organization (WHO) report states that one third of women in the world, or around 736 million of the total female population, have experienced physical or sexual violence (BBC Indonesia, 10/03/2021). This data is the result of a survey in 161 countries during 2000-2018.

Among low-income countries, WHO notes that violence against women is increasingly common. Nearly one in four women (37%) living in these countries are victims of violence. WHO concludes that violence occurs in every country and culture. Often cultural products and social institutions tend to legitimize patriarchal hegemony which leads to gender-based violence. Indonesia is one of the countries with the highest levels of violence against women and children. The findings of the National Commission on Violence against Women (*Komnas Perempuan*) noted that for 12 years (2001-2012), at least 35 women were victims of sexual violence every day. From this data, it is stated that what occurs most often is violence against young women and minors.

In 2022, National Commission on Violence against Women reported that there were 457,895 cases of violence against women. A total of 339,782 cases of this number were gender-based violence. In aggregate, National Commission on Violence against Women data shows sexual violence as the most dominant form of violence against women, namely 2,228 cases (38.21%) followed by psychological violence with 2,083 cases (35.72%). Meanwhile, data from service institutions is dominated by physical violence with 6,001 cases (38.8%), followed by sexual violence with 4,102 cases (26.52%). National Commission on Violence against Women noted that the characteristics of victims and perpetrators were still the same, namely that victims tended to be younger and had a lower level of education than the perpetrators. Meanwhile, 8.6% of the perpetrators were people who should be the protectors, such as parents, relatives, teachers, lecturers, work superiors, law enforcers and religious figures.

Referring to Law Number 23 of 2004 concerning the Elimination of Domestic Violence, sexual violence is understood as a form of domestic violence (Article 8). There are two types of sexual violence, namely: 1) forced sexual relations carried out against people who live within the household; 2) forcing sexual relations on someone within the household with another person for commercial purposes and/or certain purposes.

In the view of classical legal theory, an act of violence refers to behavior that is contrary to the law, whether in the form of a threat or a real action and has the consequences of damage to property or physical condition up to death. Criminologists then often use the term violent crime. Clinard, Quinney & Wilderman (2014), for example, use the term violent personal crime to group various forms of violent crime, such as rape, murder, and assault. In this study, researchers focus on forms of sexual violent crimes, which also contain elements of violence.

The many cases of sexual violence that have surfaced in Indonesia are actually just the tip of the iceberg of many other cases that have not been revealed. Even if they are successfully uncovered, these cases simply evaporate without a legal resolution that provides a sense of justice for the victims. The Indonesian Judicial Research Society (IJRS) survey in 2020 found that 57.0% of sexual violence cases did not receive a resolution. As many as 39.9% of cases were resolved by the perpetrator paying a certain amount of money; the victim married the perpetrator (26.2%); through a peaceful settlement (23.8%); and the perpetrator was sentenced to prison (19.2%) (IJRS, 16/03/2021). This data was later confirmed by data from the National Commission on Violence Against Women in 2021, which found that of 7,924 cases of gender-based violence, as many as 85% had no information about the resolution. Meanwhile, 948 cases were resolved through legal channels (12%) and 233 cases through non-legal channels (3%).

The findings of IJRS and National Commission on Violence against Women (*Komnas Perempuan*) show that the handling of sexual violence cases has not focused on justice and legal certainty for victims. This is important considering that according to IJRS findings, one of the reasons is because there are still officials who side more with the perpetrator than the victim. The authorities tend to intimidate and blame, even terrorize, so that many victims end up apologizing and withdrawing their reports from the police. Some even experienced repeated victimization during the investigation. Victimization is a process that gives rise to victims, losses, or injuries (Fisher & Reysn (2009), or asymmetric interpersonal relationships that are painful, destructive, parasitic and unfair (Karmen, 2010).

This culture of blaming the victim is also reflected in a survey conducted by IJRS in 2020 which found that people have views that blame the victim (victim blaming); that sexual violence can occur as a result of the victim's behavior and life choices. Most respondents thought that sexual violence was partly caused by the victim's attitude. This shows that public perception still tends to blame the victim's sexuality, especially women (IJRS, 16/03/2021). They are used to accusing women of being partly responsible for the sexual violence they experience. It often happens that the community contributes to providing tolerance to the perpetrator so that they escape the law. This reality cannot be separated from the strong patriarchal cultural construction in society.

The problem of revictimization makes victims even more trapped. Sellin and Wolfgang in their 1964 study identified three levels of victim impact, namely primary, secondary, and tertiary victimization (Burgess, et al., 2009). Primary victimization affects victims who are personally targeted or personalized. Then, secondary victimization involves impersonal, commercial, and collective victims. This type of victimization has not spread to the community or society. At the highest level, victims experience tertiary victimization whose impacts are more widespread and widespread in society, such as violations of public order, social norms, or government administration. The level of victimization often makes victims reluctant to report to the police and prefer informal institutions.

This reality raises the question of how the policing model can improve victim-friendly law enforcement services. A policing model that positions and emphasizes victim involvement in the criminal justice system as the key to victim healing and reducing costs (Clark, 2003). For this reason, in this study, researchers conducted a comparative study of police services in three countries, namely Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand. This comparative study is intended to look at the similarities and differences in policing models, while offering a victim-oriented humanistic policing approach as a policing model that can be applied in relation to handling victims of sexual violence.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical discussion related to the development of the concept of victim-oriented policing (VOP) in this research is related to the shift in policing policy by placing victims as the core consumers and the heart of every police response as stated by Paterson (022, p. 3). Through the VOP model, it is hoped that aspects of procedural justice will be promoted, ensuring that victims receive a positive response through the police as agents appointed by the community. For this reason, the theories in discussion consist of VOP, victimology, criminal policy, and democratic policing.

2.1. Victimology

In criminology, discussion of the concept of victim is related to victimology, which has become an integral part of criminology. The definition of victim is given by criminal law or given by the self-evident nature of their suffering (Walklate, 2012, p. 173). Victimology experts view that the concept of victim is the result of the constructed nature of the legal system, where victim and perpetrator are socially relevant meanings decided by legislators. These decisions are influenced by the cultural standards and value preferences of powerful social groups. Even though there is considerable disagreement in defining victims (Strobl, 2010, p. 2), victimological constructions related to victims are able to provide new insights and attempt to reproduce both official and subjective victim constructions. Victimology firmly places the needs and rights of victims on its agenda. The concept of victims' rights has had a major influence on the formation of criminal justice policies both at home and abroad. Internationally, victims' rights are classified into two large groups.

First, victims have rights for services rights or social rights, which summarize the special rights provided by the state for victims after a crime occurs, including (Doak, 2014, p. 5445): (1) service rights, namely the victim's right to obtain various kinds social services or rights; (2) compensation, that crime victims must be able to exercise the right to receive compensation after violent crimes that cause death or bodily injury; (3) special measures, trying to avoid secondary victimization in the courtroom.

Second, victims have procedural rights which require some form of participation in the criminal procedure itself, including (Doak, 2014, p. 5469): (1) procedural rights: procedural rights require some form of participation by the victim in criminal procedures; (2) participation in the trial process: the victim's ability to participate actively in the trial process is generally limited; and (3) victim participation in sentencing: participation in sentencing procedures is more common than participation in the actual trial.

Victimization has several meanings. According to Fisher & Reynolds (2009, p.162), victimization is the outcome of deliberate action taken by a person or institution to exploit, oppress, or harm another, or to destroy or illegally obtain another's property or possessions. Meanwhile, Karmen (2010, p.2), defines victimization as an asymmetrical interpersonal relationship that is abusive, painful, destructive, parasitical, and unfair. Meanwhile Doerner & Lab (2012, p.4) say that victimization can also be defined as a dyadic relationship between the perpetrator of the crime and the victim of the crime.

Victimization itself has a typology consisting of five categories based on the relationship between the victim and the perpetrator (Sellin & Wolfgang, 1964), namely: (1) primary victimization; (2) secondary victimization; (3) tertiary victimization; (4) mutual victimization; and (5) no victimization (Wemmers, 2014).

2.2. Victim-Oriented Policing

VOP principles include several operational dimensions (Paterson & Williams, 2018, pp. 89-93; Paterson, 2022, pp. 1-6). First, find ways to deal with primary or secondary victimization, and reduce the effects of victimization on society. Second, use repeat victimization as a performance indicator and naturally allocate police resources to high crime areas and to targets that cause the most victims. Third, place the police as first responders for vulnerable people through pre-emptive warnings. Fourth, increased focus on understanding the impact of policing through a vulnerability lens, including the individual, social and institutional vulnerabilities that will be faced. Fifth, prioritize victims' needs and collaboration. Sixth, building collaborative goals for those who carry out informal and formal policing functions in democratic societies. Seventh, form collaborations with communities most at risk of harm and develop strategies for how they collectively conceptualize policing needs. Eighth, emphasize the social, political, legal and ideological harmony of structure, governance, partnerships, roles, functions, training and education for the conceptualization of victim-based policing.

The VOP strategy is believed to increase public trust in the police (Paterson, 2022, p. 6). For police officers, this strategy is an efficient way to allocate police resources effectively to help victims, prevent repeat victimization, and police officers can obtain positive feedback from victims (Farrell, 2001, p. 199).

In this VOP context, Indonesia is still uncertain in implementing VOP through the principles of restorative justice. Because even though there is diversion where victims receive healing support and victims participate in the criminal justice system, victim offender mediation efforts in the form of mediation between the perpetrator and the victim are still oriented towards the perpetrator. Recovery of the victim is only part of the conditions set, which as far as possible keeps the perpetrator away from the crime (Dinata, 2020, p. 52).

2.3. Democratic Policing

The VOP concept is then linked to the concept of democratic policing which allows political and government processes to be carried out through the principles of public accountability which emphasize transparency, checks and balances, and the supremacy of the law. Jerome H Skolnick (1999), the originator of the idea of democratic policing, said that the policing system also follows a country's government system, whether it is democratic, authoritarian, and so on. In the democratic era, the appropriate policing model to apply is democratic policing (Karnavian & Sulistyono, 2017). Skolnick assesses that the emergence of democratic policing is in line with the transition of political ideology in various parts of the world which is slowly changing towards democracy.

Skolnick (1999:2) states: "... democratic police forces are not supposed to be insular, self-contained, or cut off from the communities from which their power derives. Openness to the free and the poor should be a master ideal of democratic policing." This statement means that democratic policing should be open and involving the public, inclusive of various groups and layers of society, as a source of legitimacy for police institutions. Skolnick emphasized that democratic policing practices can be realized by emphasizing two important aspects, namely openness and accountability.

Democratic policing provides guidance for the police to pay attention to community problems and further collaborate with the community to gain legitimacy. Experts emphasize that democratic policing is a concept that emphasizes that the police are the public and the public is the police, where cooperation between the community and the police is policing that comes from the community, through policy making that is discussed with the community and the actions of the police themselves. In other words, the essence of democratic policing is consent on the part of the community. The key to democratic policing lies in public legitimacy, which means the community is the object of police security (Karnavian & Sulistyono, 2017).

According to Roberson & Mire (2009), the concept of democratic policing contains several important notes regarding characteristics. First, the police must work in accordance with democratic principles, namely being professional, understanding human rights standards, and acting in accordance with legal provisions. Second, the police uphold the ethical values and norms that apply in society and institutions. Third, the police must have top priority in securing and protecting people's lives. Fourth, the police always serve the community selflessly and are responsible to the community. Fifth, provide protection for life and property. Sixth, police actions must be in accordance with human dignity and human rights. Lastly, the police are neutral and non-discriminatory.

2.4. Criminal Policy

The practical manifestation of criminal policy is society's decisions regarding crime or actions against crime. Research on criminal policy approaches general legal policy research and applied criminology, making it a form of scholarship that takes a place alongside research on criminal law and criminology (Lahti, 2000). In its development, criminal policy uses an evidence-based approach which includes a commitment from prevention science to the use of the most scientifically valid studies to evaluate a program (Welsh & Farrington, 2012). In other words, this approach seeks to increase the influence of research on policy formation, especially criminal policy. Criminal policy can be carried out repressively through the "penal" criminal justice system, it can also be carried out using "non-penal" means through various prevention efforts without involving the criminal justice system.

Hoefnagels (1969) emphasized that criminal policy is a social reaction to crime in the form of the establishment of an institution. Within the scope of this criminal policy, Hoefnagels includes: (a) the application of criminal law means; (b) prevention without punishment; and (c) efforts to influence public views about crime. Hoefnagels defines criminal policy as: 1) part of the science concerned with reactions to crime; 2) the complexity of science relating to crime prevention; 3) political steps in determining a human act that will be designated as a crime; 4) a comprehensive rational response to the phenomenon of crime. The four dimensions are condensed by defining criminal policy as a rational organization of society's reactions to crime.

In an effort to overcome crime, laws were formed. In this scope, a legislative body policy is needed to formulate prohibited acts by as carefully as possible formulating the elements of criminal acts and the types of legal sanctions (Mirzana, 2012). Policy formulation follows structured stages. This model generally includes the stages of agenda-setting, policy formulation, decision making, implementation, and evaluation (Jann & Wegrich, 2007, p. 43-51).

In Indonesia, criminal policies in dealing with the problem of sexual violence have been contained in several laws and other policy instruments. However, the existence of this law has not been able to provide optimal protection, especially for victims of sexual violence. There are still problems related to prevention, treatment,

and recovery. As in Japan, the legal and social environment tends not to provide support for victims of sexual violence, so they tend to remain silent and reluctant to report (Suzuki, 2016).

However, in the last two decades, as in New Zealand, the problem of sexual violence has been conceptualized as a public problem so that it is no longer a private matter. This means that the state can intervene and apply punishment in accordance with applicable law. There are progressive steps to promote a more inclusive reach in reaching state responsibilities and concerns (Gavey & Farley, 2020, p. 229).

3. Research Method

This research uses a descriptive-qualitative approach as an instrument to describe and understand social phenomena (Creswell, 2014) by creating a comprehensive picture presented through a detailed report (Walidin, Saifullah & Tabrani, 2015, p. 77). This approach is intended to produce new hypotheses that emphasize meaning, not generalization (Sugiyono, 2016, p. 299), based on the concept of going exploring in several cases or single cases (Denzin & Lincoln, 2017). Through this approach, we explore data in depth regarding the subject and object of research, namely the Indonesian, Japanese and New Zealand Police using the comparative case study method.

According to Neuman (2013, p.536), case study comparative research is research that compares one or two cultures or cultural units in depth. The comparative case study method is used by placing the state and police institutions as the object and context of research. In accordance with this research method, we compared the forms of service between police organizations in three countries in dealing with victims of sexual violence crimes. Comparisons were made on service group elements related to organizational culture, resources and special police competencies. The results of the analysis of the various variables that were compared then became the basis for us to create a model related to victim-oriented humanistic policing (VOHP) for adaptation in Indonesia.

Research data sources consist of primary and secondary data sources. Primary data sources were obtained from interviews with informants who were considered to represent the data perspective that supports this research study. There were 20 selected informants who came from three countries with different institutional backgrounds in the police, non-state institutions, NGOs, and professionals. The interview process for informants will be carried out throughout 2022-2023. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from previous research, documents, journals, books, and mass media. In collecting data, we used in-depth interview techniques, observation, and document study. So that the data used has high validity, we use triangulation analysis techniques by using other cases as comparisons (Moleong, 2014). Then we interpret the data using a framework of thought or a framework of existing concepts and theories. The aim is to draw conclusions that support theoretical hypotheses and recommendations for improving future studies (Kriyantono, 2012, p. 87).

4. Result and Discussion

The discussion and research results begin with an explanation of the policing model in serving sexual violence crime cases in three countries, namely Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand. We explain several relevant and important findings, before then carrying out comparisons for the purpose of hypothesizing to offer a more victim-oriented humanistic policing model.

4.1. Indonesia

What is generally known about the Indonesian Police or National Police in providing services to victims of crimes of sexual violence is that there is no Chief of the Indonesian National Police Regulation (in Bahasa Indonesia: *Peraturan Kapolri* or *Perkap*) that regulates procedures for handling victims. The existing *Perkap* only covers general mechanisms and standard operating procedures (SOP) and does not touch on technical matters in the field. Polda Metro Jaya already has an SOP regarding handling cases of women and children and plans to implement it nationally (Hanita and Nurherwati, 2022). The SOP contains guidelines for questions,

references and all matters related to the process of investigating women and children's cases. Every investigator serving in the Women and Children Services Unit (*Unit Pelayanan Perempuan dan Anak* or *PPA*) is required to follow the legal process guidelines that have been established and follow the SOP as an action procedure. However, practically, the SOP is still only a written guide because in the field, handling is carried out according to police discretion.

In line with the increase in digital activism through social media, police informants (04/04/2023) admitted that the police were starting to make improvements. Including visiting the victim to dig up the legal truth. However, high levels of public intervention sometimes make the police go awry because the opinions that develop on social media do not necessarily match the facts. For this reason, the police develop cases based on legal facts and evidence. In cases of sexual violence, the most important legal evidence is a post-mortem. If there is no evidence or witnesses, the victim will be directed to undergo a post-mortem examination. During the investigation process, the victim will usually be satisfied if the perpetrator is successfully caught. Sometimes, when the perpetrator is willing to pay for the victim's treatment, the report can be withdrawn. In other words, the case was resolved using restorative justice or outside the formal justice system.

During the handling process, the Women and Children Services Unit (*Unit Pelayanan Perempuan dan Anak* or *PPA*) will bridge coordination with the Technical Implementation Unit of the Integrated Service Center for the Empowerment of Women and Children (*Unit Pelaksana Teknis Pusat Pelayanan Terpadu Pemberdayaan Perempuan dan Anak* or *P2TP2A*) and the Witness and Victim Protection Agency (*Lembaga Perlindungan Saksi dan Korban* or *LPSK*). Regarding the protection of victims at the Witness and Victim Protection Agency, the informant said there were four main criteria as regulated by Law No. 31 of 2014 concerning Protection of Witnesses and Victims. The four criteria include the type of crime (light/medium/severe), status (victim/perpetrator/witness/other), level of threat and track record.

However, so far, the victims' rights have not been fully fulfilled. This is because of the complicated bureaucratic system and applicable legal logic. Many perpetrators are also unable to pay compensation, so they prefer punishment. This is because generally victims of violence in Indonesia want the losses they have experienced to be returned. Sometimes the compensation or restitution paid by the perpetrator to the victim does not have a definite value, so the victim tends to set a high price as the cost of compensation/restitution. This practice often occurs, and victims are like collectors. Under The Law on Sexual Violence Crimes (*Undang-Undang Tindak Pidana Kekerasan Seksual* or *UU TPKS*), perpetrators who are unable to pay compensation can use the Victim Assistance Fund which is managed by the state. However, until now, according to the informant (12/04/2023), there are no derivative regulations that regulate the technical implementation.

The availability of organizational resources for the National Police is still very limited. Be it human resources, budget, or infrastructure. If Polda Metro Jaya has adequate resources due to special arrangements, this is not the case with other jurisdictions. The availability of resources is important to support the process of handling violence cases so that it becomes easy, cheap, and fast. Limited resources cause many cases to be neglected, resulting in long-term losses for victims.

One of the human resources that is most needed is a special investigator to handle cases of sexual violence. Based on data obtained from Polda Metro Jaya, there are 140 PPA investigators recorded, of which 13 investigators are certified. Polda Metro Jaya also has 81 special investigators for women and children in the Sub-directorate of Youth, Children and Women of the Criminal Investigation Department (*Subdirektorat Remaja, Anak, dan Wanita* or *Renakta*), and 18 of them are certified. Even though there is a contribution of resources from Integrated Service Center for the Empowerment of Women and Children and the Witness and Victim Protection Agency, the human resources for special investigators at the National Police are still centralized and limited to Polda Metro Jaya. This limited human resource threatens the professionalism and quality of the National Police in handling cases. Even though it is supported by the Integrated Service Center for the Empowerment of Women and Children and the Witness and Victim Protection Agency, the availability of human resources is not yet fully adequate. This was acknowledged by three informants whom we interviewed separately on 4th, 10th, and 14th of April, 2023.

To improve special competencies, the National Police is actively holding several integrated education and training programs. During training, there is usually training and simulations on ways to conduct victim-friendly interviews. At Polda Metro Jaya there are seminars, workshops, focus group discussions and similar activities to improve the competency of investigators. Those who took technical guidance based on an order from Polda Metro Jaya had previously received training from the Women and Children Services Unit in stages. However, it must be acknowledged that finding special investigators for women and children is not easier than detective investigators. Because to become a special investigator requires special standards and criteria that can be known since recruitment. Meanwhile, interest in becoming an investigator specifically for women and children is very low. According to an informant from the police (10th of April, 2023), they took part in training to obtain a child investigator certificate.

Apart from the lack of special investigators, the Integrated Service Center for the Empowerment of Women and Children and the Witness and Victim Protection Agency in many areas are not functioning. There is still overlap between the Women and Children Services Unit and the Integrated Service Center for the Empowerment of Women and Children. While the latter institutions generally come from NGOs, the the Women and Children Services Unit all contain government employees in accordance with The Law on Sexual Violence Crimes. This difference in names tends to hamper institutional performance. On the other hand, the Witness and Victim Protection Agency also has limited human resources, especially for psychologists, so they must be brought in from outside. There are plans to develop human resources and organizational wings to around 18 representative regions. So far, the Witness and Victim Protection Agency already has two regional representatives, namely in Medan and Yogyakarta. Soon, the Witness and Victim Protection Agency will form representatives in NTT and the Riau Islands because they are areas with the highest rates of Trafficking in Persons (TIP) cases and sexual violence. This confession was conveyed by an informant from the Witness and Victim Protection Agency (12th of April, 2023).

Infrastructure and budget are far from expectations. Even though the National Police budget continues to increase from year to year, the impact on law enforcement performance is not yet significant. The availability of special care homes for women and children, safe houses, accommodation for victims' families, hospitals and other supporting services is still limited. Informants said that Polda Metro Jaya was one of the fastest to carry out transformation. For example, there are referral hospitals, free post-mortems, and medical service facilities. However, there is still overlapping authority and it is not evenly distributed throughout Indonesia, according to an informant from a member of the PPA police unit (10/04/2023). This reality then gave birth to technological innovation in the form of the Help RENAHTA application. The informant said this application was used in DKI Jakarta and would be implemented in all regions. This application was developed with the aim of increasing the sense of security for women and children; provide access to information, knowledge, education, and skills for victims to report, consult and ask for help, etc. Apart from that, there is the Integrated Criminal Investigation Department Administration System Application (*Sistem Administrasi Ditreskrim Terpadu* or *SIMADU*) (Hanita and Hurherwati, 2022). Web-based application created at the Ditreskrim Polda Metro Jaya as a solution to public complaints regarding incomplete handling of police reports, piling up of case file archives in storage space so that a digital storage system is needed.

4.2. Japan

The Japanese police began a democratization process after World War II, to be precise since 1948. At that time, the Public Security Commission system was born which marked a change in the structure of the national police to regional police to ensure decentralized management of power (Young, 2019). In the past, the laws, and regulations regarding the Japanese Police (Police Act) created a rigid structure, centralized authority, and an abundance of one-way and overlapping authority. Apart from that, inefficiencies arise in each operation due to wasted operational costs (Hopkins & Flemington, 2009).

Since 1980, four years after the bomb incident at the Mitsubishi factory, two special laws and regulations have emerged that regulate the urgency of dealing with victims of criminal acts. The first regulation is called the

Crime Victims Benefit Payment Law, which is an official Japanese government regulation that regulates compensation and compensation for relatives of victims who have suffered because of criminal acts. The second regulation is called the Benefit System for Crime Victims, namely the administrative details that must be implemented to supremacy the first regulation (Kawabata, Tseng, & Crick, 2014). Based on this initiative, support for meeting the economic needs of victims of criminal acts began to be implemented in Japan. After 10 years, the system has become increasingly consolidated. This is driven by awareness of the importance of paying attention to the welfare of victims (Japanese National Police Agency, 2023, p. 6).

For Japan, crime victims, including victims of sexual violence, certainly experience severe trauma (Kawabata, 2020). For this reason, the Japanese National Police Agency pays great attention to the four principles of crime victim services, namely (1) accompanying; (2) listening; (3) explain: and (4) protect. The principle of accompanying is carried out by visiting the victim as soon as possible after the incident occurs, so that there is a positive emotional exchange in the form of sympathy and empathy (Ismawansa, Ablisar, & Shahrin, 2022). Furthermore, the NPA schedules visits to hospitals, accompanies and is willing to provide explanations regarding crime incidents, provides a free pick-up and drop-off service for victims from the police post, the crime scene, to the victim's house.

The principle of listening is carried out by being a listener to the victim's complaints and always being willing to answer to become a problem-solving agent who is a solution to the victim's problems. The principle explains by providing a guidebook for the case at hand entitled *To the Victims of Crime*. It explains the progress of the investigation along with a collection of procedures that still need to be implemented, explains the issues that must be handled in court in the future, and provides additional explanatory assistance for those closest to the victim such as relatives, neighbours, friends at school, or colleagues. In principle, protection is carried out in the form of contact at least once a week via email.

In general, victims of criminal acts generally get three rights, namely insurance for victims targeted by murderers, medical insurance, and life insurance (Abbey & McAuslan, 2004). The amount of insurance that the Japanese National Police Agency can offer to each victim is a maximum of 1.2 million yen. The insurance policy offered covers within a year of the incident occurring. It's just that this requires evidence, such as a doctor's letter, examination fees, recovery fees, and other costs. According to police investigators and service informants to us (25/04/2022), there is also a system called compensation which is distributed to victims. If there is a victim who suffers major losses, for example death, serious injuries and so on, the victim should receive compensation from the perpetrator and the central government. However, those from the central government are not given when the perpetrator and victim are related by blood or are related to the Yakuza or are foreign nationals.

In terms of sexual violent crimes, the Japanese National Police Agency considers them to be criminal acts that result in "huge losses to the state" (Ohbuchi, Ishige, Yamanoha, & Inoue, 1985). This assessment is based on Japan's promise to provide happiness for every citizen, including sexual happiness. In dealing with this type of crime, what the Japanese National Police Agency carried out was scheduling supervisory investigators as instructors for sexual violent crime investigations (Polaschek & Ward, 2002). As in Indonesia, the investigation process is carried out by female National Police Agency agents (Ward, 2000). This female National Police Agency is tasked with interviewing victims, collecting evidence, accompanying victims to the hospital, providing the latest news regarding investigation developments, and carrying out other additional actions necessary to facilitate the success of the program.

The next effort was to establish a consultation center for sexual violent crimes (Katsuta & Hazama, 2016), where departments in each prefecture established counseling services via a contact number, namely 110. The service was carried out by female National Police agents. Another effort is to provide financial assistance (Nunes & Jung, 2013). Most of the financial assistance that occurs in Japan is intended to cover the costs of purchasing contraceptive equipment to prevent births for victims. Another thing that is unique about the Japanese National Police Agency in responding to sexual violent crimes is the formation of special officers to handle cases that occur on trains. The Japanese National Police Agency established a special division called the railway police. This division has a sub-division called female victim counselling officers. In an office with a special room, a

female National Police agent responds to reports from victims who call the contact number 110. The officer will accompany the victim to the train carriage where the incident occurred, and even accompany the victim to change trains if there is an emergency.

In general, the support system for crime victims is very intensive. The victim will be assisted during the recovery period for more than three months. They realized that the victim must have experienced mental changes because of the crimes they experienced. "For this reason, we will accompany them by providing moral or mental support, while explaining how the criminal process works and other things." (Interview with informant from NPA Japan, 04/25/2022).

Although Japan has made great progress in systems and policies for crime victims since 2004, what is not easy to overcome is rebuilding the lives and support of victims in the long term. Another issue that is of serious concern to the Japanese National Police Agency is public attention to restorative justice. This approach was initiated by *Chiba's Taiwa no Kai* (a kind of consulting association) which was founded in 2001 (Ito, 2016). This association bridges the dialogue between victims and perpetrators in juvenile cases.

In order to improve human resources and special competency in handling cases, the Japanese NPA has special training carried out at the National Police Academy Institute. This training is referred to as "recruitment training" and is trained directly by newly recruited officers to eradicate the problem of sexual violent crimes by being signed or formalized directly by each prefectural police chief. The time to carry out this training is 15 months for academy alumni. Meanwhile, the time to carry out this training is 21 months for high school graduates and equivalent. This program is designed to resource agents who are intimately aware of the victim's feelings to prevent secondary victimization (Yamagami, 2008).

4.3. New Zealand

The New Zealand Police has the main vision of making New Zealand the safest and most comfortable country for people wherever they are. the New Zealand Police main vision is Safe Home, Safe Road, and Safe Community. In achieving this goal, the New Zealand Police explained to its members throughout the country as well as several external partners about how to carry out prevention, crime and danger prevention forecasts, and capabilities and strengthening partnership organizations. In almost the last decade, KSB has also placed 'evidence-based policing' as one of the main drivers of change. "New Zealand has very high ambitions to be the safest country on the planet. So, it's really about results, about evidence." (Interview with informant from New Zealand Police, 09/09/2022).

The organizational transformation began when the New Zealand Police received its legislative mandate from the 2008 Policing Act, which states that "a police service with effective and efficient principles is the foundation of a free and democratic society under the rule of law." Even though there is a formal mandate in law, public trust and confidence is the most important support for New Zealand Police (police.govt.nz, 12/04/2023). New Zealand Police considers that approval from the community is the main thing to be able to carry out the functions regulated by law. New Zealand Police regularly measures public trust and confidence in police services and actively adapts to community demands. So, the its policing style is stated to be different from many other countries in the world. Its policing focus adheres to the teaching that every interaction and communication is an opportunity to prevent harm. New Zealand Police recognizes that by involving, educating, and encouraging communities to work together, they often achieve more positive results.

New Zealand Police attention to victims, including victims of sexual violence, is very comprehensive by placing and prioritizing victims' rights. Victims' rights include the rights to receive assistance, protection, and support. In the case of victims of serious crimes, the victim has the right to apply for a program called a victim notification system (VNS) to remain informed about what happened to the perpetrator while undergoing the justice process. Even for victims under 17 years old, their parents or legal guardians can act as representatives of the victim in this program (corrections.govt.nz, 14th of April, 2023).

Another victim's right that is considered important is the victim's right to be accompanied by someone during the legal process, such as a lawyer and legal advisor for legal support or a counsellor for mental support for victims whether they have experienced trauma or not (victimsinfo.govt.nz, 14 /04/2023). The next right is the victim's right to receive compensation and financial support. The purpose of this right is to restore losses suffered because of crime, including emotional losses or loss of property. Victims of serious crimes also have the right to apply for financial support called a victim assistance scheme (VAS). This program is managed by Victim Support on behalf of the Ministry of Justice and is limited to victims who have experienced sexual violent crimes and serious crimes.

The informant who is the national coordinator of adult sexual assault (ASA) at the New Zealand Police, told us (5th of September, 2022) that his party's goal is to ensure excellent service to victims of sexual harassment and child abuse, and placing them as a priority. In the last 10-12 years, the New Zealand Police has had staff dedicated to carrying out child protection work, and staff specifically dealing with adult sexual violence. According to Sharyn Tichener, manager of the International Child Protection Unit, Ministry for Vulnerable Children (Oranga, Tamariki), the New Zealand Police has so far implemented victim-centered policing. "I found that police policy was already very victim-centred. They are very good at understanding that first the needs and rights of the child must come before prosecution." (Interview with child protection manager informant, 6th of September, 2022).

In carrying out its main duties, the New Zealand Police partners with a multi-agency center (MAC) as a center for victims of child abuse or adult sexual violence. The child abuse category is victims under 18 years old. MAC talks not only about victims, but also regarding family losses, treatment, especially the traumatic conditions of victims. In a direct interview with the MAC team, it was stated that they were social workers who worked with the police to provide care for victims of crimes of sexual violence, as well as victims of robbery and murder. "We are here to support the family and the police in the reporting process, whether it is an initial statement or a full statement being made." (Interview with four informants from MAC, 9th of September, 2022).

New Zealand Police also provides community guidance so that they are responsive in calling the police on 111 if they experience a security situation. This method is part of a method that continues to be developed in schools and social workers who interact with many families. All of this involves Oranga Tamariki and other agencies providing support in keeping children safe and addressing their needs.

To support its services, New Zealand Police utilizes NEAR, a national intelligence application. The application records all reported incidents or crimes so that New Zealand Police can track the location and topic of the crime. The NEAR app is designed to help officers make health-based referrals, serve as evidence, and aid decision making. Even through the crime loss index, New Zealand Police can see who the most dangerous people are, who the victims are most harmed by, where the most dangerous places are. In this way, police officers have data, performance reporting, research continuous improvement, and evaluation and service design. There is also a mobility device where all offices have access to an application called Checkpoint, which functions as a checklist. Most of the New Zealand Police frontline officers also had access to two MP4 rifles and two Glocks in a lock box in the back of the car. They are available to be deployed for any critical incident or emergency. "So we've also developed the New Zealand Crime Danger Index. Now, we can use that information combined with crime volume and service causes so we can better allocate resources." (Interview with informant from the Evidence-Based Policing Center, 9th of September, 2022).

In increasing member competency, New Zealand Police has a kind of evidence-based police center intranet portal that can be clicked on by every member. On the website, there are videos of statements from crime victims in New Zealand. Every officer can access via cell phone, and learn from the many experiences of experts about criminal evidence, so that they do not risk failing to prosecute or doing things that are unsafe for themselves or the organization. Apart from that, New Zealand Police also creates databases, for example with the University of Queensland as one of its strategic partners. There is a kind of 'global police database house' containing half a million records.

On the other hand, there is regular training on child protection for those in child protection police units, and any social worker can even apply for a job at the Ministry of Children (Oranga Tamariki). That training they must go through, every few months, not only about child protection, also about privacy laws.

4.4. VOP Comparison: Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand

The research results show that there are elements of similarities as well as differences in police models and services for victims of sexual violence crimes in the three countries: Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand. Below we explain the similarities and differences.

4.4.1. Elements of Similarities

Historically, the police forces in the three countries were both European products. This is more because both Indonesia and New Zealand, except Japan, were colonized by Europeans. Even though it was not colonized by Europeans, Japan has had good relations with European countries to this day. The origins of the Japanese Police or NPA began when in 1872 the Japanese government sent General Toshiyoshi Kawaji to Europe to study the police system. Returning from Europe, Kawaji founded the Tokyo Metropolitan Police Department which worked under the Ministry of the Interior in 1874. This organization is known as Japan's first modern police organization and its system was built based on continental concepts under the juridical institutions of the Meiji Empire era. At that time, the formation of the Japanese Police was entirely the result of a merger between systems from Germany and France which then changed their function to regulate citizens since experiencing democratization after World War II in 1948 when the police law was issued.

Even though the Indonesian Police did not learn from Western countries, colonialism by the Dutch for 350 years helped form the seeds of the National Police organization. The form of policing began with the formation of a security force in Semarang in 1867 to guard the assets and wealth of the colonial nation. Over time, the organizational structure of the Indonesian National Police continues to adapt according to the political system until it reaches the form that was established in the era of independence and the most modern since the *Reformasi*. Because it is a European product, it indirectly creates similar organizational structures, responsibilities, and authorities in the three countries.

One of the police structures that is the same in all three countries is the level of organization from the center to the regions. These organizational levels have the same duties and functions with different authorities. In Japan, the regional police level is called Prefecture, while in Indonesia it is called Polda/Polres. This hierarchical structure shows the decentralization of police power. The duties and functions of the police in the three countries are the same, namely maintaining security and social order, preventing crime and taking action against criminals, as well as traffic and investigating crime cases.

Apart from that, the police in the three countries also have supporting institutions. Indonesia and Japan have institutions supporting police institutions such as academies and special units. In Indonesia, it is known as the Police Academy (Akpil) and Staff and Leadership School (Sespim) which provide human resources to ensure the availability of officers who can fill structural positions at the central to regional levels. Meanwhile, the Japanese National Police Agency also has three institutions under it, namely the National Police Academy, the National Police Scientific Institute, and the Emperor's Escort Command Center. The National Police Academy is tasked with providing training in leadership investigations, international crime research and Interpol cooperation, as well as skills in public relations and communication with citizens (Miyakoshi & Kasahara, 2003).

In carrying out their main duties and functions, the three countries are committed to increasing police competence in terms of mastery of technology, law enforcement, especially for female and child investigators. Police officers are also trained and nurtured to understand technology so they are able to adapt to changes. The police also have a database center that can be used as a source and information center that is easily accessible. In contrast to Indonesia, which is still in the development stage, both countries are more advanced in terms of

information and data transparency. Victims' access to police officers becomes easier and facilitated with the existence of a reporting and data center.

In terms of services for victims, the police in all three countries have special investigators. The special investigator referred to is a female police officer (*polisi wanita* or *polwan*). They were assigned to investigate cases of sexual violence that befell women and children. The involvement of policewomen is intended as an effort to make the victim comfortable and not pressured when talking about the case that happened to him. During investigations, the police always involve supervisory investigators. In Japan, there are supervisory investigators who serve as instructors in cases experienced by women, while in Indonesia there is supervision from police officers during the interview process with victims. Based on National Police Regulation Number 5 of 2019 concerning Amendments to Chief of the Indonesian National Police Regulation (in Bahasa Indonesia: *Peraturan Kapolri* or *Perkap*) Number 6 of 2017 concerning Organizational Structure and Work Administration (*Susunan Organisasi dan Tata Kerja* or *SOTK*) at Police Headquarters, the implementation of supervision, assistance and carrying out case titles for cases that are being investigated by investigators is carried out by the Investigator Supervision Bureau (*Biro Pengawasan Penyidik* or *Rowassidik*).

Apart from that, the police in all three countries have the same commitment to fulfill victims' rights from treatment to recovery. The rights of victims served can include legal assistance by a lawyer, psychological assistance by a counselor, medical assistance by a doctor, testimony before a trial to restitution and financial support (compensation) from the government. In handling cases of violence, the police always involve other institutions or parties. Strategic partnerships demonstrate a comprehensive service model that can help the police handle cases.

4.4.2. Elements of Differences

Institutionally, there are several differences in policing in the three countries. First, related to the vision and mission. In Indonesia, the National Police's vision and mission often change according to changes in leadership within the organization. Each National Police Chief has his own slogan as his leadership vision and mission. This is different from the New Zealand Police which has the main slogan: Safe Home, Safe Road, and Safe Community. This slogan has the main vision of making New Zealand the safest and most comfortable country for people wherever they are. Meanwhile, Japan has a standard and well-organized vision and mission so that this institution has helped the country get out of the vulnerability of criminal risks.

Second, community involvement. In contrast to Indonesia, New Zealand Police is very strongly supported by the community. For KSB, approval from the community is the main thing to be able to carry out the functions regulated by law. Likewise in Japan, the National Police Agency has become an agent that merges with everyday life in the eyes of citizens who obey regulations and indeed support the preservation of public order. In Indonesia, there has been decentralization of police power, but often law enforcement authority is transferred to the National Police Headquarters. Community involvement has not been a concern and instead tends to be seen as an obstacle.

Third, partnerships with local tribes. In New Zealand, New Zealand Police partners with Māori to address legal issues. The police recognize the role that organizations can play to seek better resolutions for Māori and actively change the current over-representation of Māori in the criminal justice system, through self-reflection, improving services and meeting the priorities set by Iwi and Māori. In Indonesia, the National Police has not yet accommodated certain cultures into the justice system.

Fourth, integrity. In New Zealand and Japan, the police strictly maintain their integrity, ethics, professionalism, and competence. Every police officer who violates the law is subject to criminal sanctions. This is different from Indonesia's case, when the National Police is under scrutiny because of the cases of its members, there are more and more violations by members. The National Police also tends to protect its members who violate the law on the pretext that the actions of one member do not represent the organization. In other cases, police officers who break the law are not immediately dismissed.

Fifth, victims are a priority. In Japan, the National Police Agency has the basic principles of providing services to crime victims, starting from mentoring, listening, explaining to providing protection. For the Japanese NPA, victims of sexual violent crimes are seen as a loss to the country. Likewise in New Zealand, New Zealand Police prioritizes victims in handling cases. During treatment, they strive to ensure that victims do not experience pressure and discrimination. In contrast to Indonesia, the police often determine the priority scale because they receive incentives from the victim or perpetrator. This results in handling legal cases without professionalism and integrity. Not to mention the finding that the Indonesian police tend to protect the perpetrators. This includes restorative justice policies.

Sixth, welfare guarantee for victims. Both Japanese and New Zealand police are very concerned about the rights of victims of sexual violent crimes. In New Zealand, these rights can take the form of assistance, giving information at trial, and even post-trial protection. In Japan, victims have three basic rights, namely victim insurance rights, medical insurance rights, and life insurance. This is also a direct action of the state's responsibility towards its citizens to cover victims' losses. In Indonesia, when there is compensation from the perpetrator, the police often dismiss the case.

Seventh, mapping crime-prone points. In Japan, there are special officers from the NPA to prevent sexual violent crimes on trains. This is because sexual violent crime cases are quite high on trains as government policy requires people to use public transportation. There is also a mailbox at the police post which can be accessed by victims of sexual violent crimes because of the vulnerability of women to violence. The reason is that many women choose not to marry. In New Zealand, higher level police officers carry two guns in their cars ready to be deployed for any critical incident or emergency. New Zealand Police also has a national intelligence application to record all crime incidents reported by the public. The police in Indonesia have not advanced in terms of mapping crime hotspots. For public consultation facilities, these are usually available through websites and social media, but so far they have not been effective, unless the case goes viral.

Eighth, restorative justice orientation. In New Zealand and Japan, there is a push to resolve sexual violent crime cases outside formal justice or restorative justice. However, in Indonesia, the implementation of restorative justice is only for child offenders with losses under IDR 2.5 million. Meanwhile, for adult offenders, recommendations for restorative justice are not recommended. The Sexual Violence Crime Law issued in 2022 opposes policies for sexual violence cases.

Lastly, a safe house for the victim's family. In New Zealand, there are shelter homes for families who assist in handling victims' cases. In Indonesia, there are no shelter facilities for families, but there are safe houses for victims to recover. The available safe houses are not evenly distributed and are still concentrated in DKI Jakarta. Not to mention, there is still overlapping authority in managing safe houses between the central government and regional governments so that victims are often placed in safe houses far from their families.

4.4.3. Indonesian Police Victim-Oriented Humanistic Policing (VOHP) Model

Many studies reveal the weak response of the police to the case reports on physical violence and especially sexual violence. The police often consider claims of sexual violence to be baseless, so victims often experience revictimization during investigations. This is in line with the lack of empirical knowledge of police officers who handle and investigate cases of sexual violence. Not to mention that there are laws and practices that indirectly place victims in a subordinate, helpless condition and have their voices silenced (Ricciardelli, Spencer & Dodge, 2021:217). This condition will of course have an impact on the low status of victims which will then greatly influence the response of police officers (Loftus, 2009).

We offer a new model of victim-oriented humanistic policing so that it can contribute to the development of police professionalism in providing services to victims of sexual violence in Indonesia. The new model includes five approaches, namely (1) continuous assistance; (2) practical interview skills; (3) advocacy support; (4)

mastery of technology; and (5) strategic partnerships. These five approaches are the result of comparative extraction of the VOP of three countries, Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand.

4.4.4. Continuous Assistance

Assistance will be provided from the start of the report until after the trial. This approach is expected to improve services for those in need, create a sense of security, and grow victims' confidence and trust in the police. This assistance by the police also fulfils the obligations of crime victims' rights regarding medical services, providing timely and honest information, and implementing procedures and practices to prevent secondary victimization. If the victim experiences physical suffering, the police shall provide treatment for a certain period according to the required cooperation contract. During this process, the police must listen, explain, and protect the victim to support faster recovery.

In cases of sexual violence, the police response must prioritize facilitation and remedy the victim's suffering. The police must first ensure two important things, namely the victim's involvement in the investigation process and the victim's safety. This service by the police can be called hidden work which includes victim care, multi-agency collaboration, providing practical assistance, compensation, compensation, as well as efforts to protect victims from physical and psychological suffering, including post-formal trials. When the victim does not want to be involved in the investigation, the police need to collaborate with the authorities as a third party that the victim wants, to find the perpetrator. This allows victims to remain active in the decision-making process and shape the police response that the victim desires.

Studies show that interactions between victims-and-police and recovery services show a strong relationship with reduced likelihood of future violence (Xie & Lynch, 2017). In other words, victims who report to the police have a lower risk of revictimization than victims who do not report. Additionally, the risk of revictimization was significantly lower for victims who received help from recovery agencies. This victim assistance service needs to be included in formal assessments of police performance, apart from the main performance around prevention success and arrest rates.

4.4.5. Practical Interview Skills

Interview skills are one of the special competencies that sexual violence case investigators must have. Interviewing skills refer to the investigator's ability to gather information and draw conclusions from the victim. These skills help police officers and professionals examine topics closely and discover important things that may not be apparent to those without these skills. Investigators with adequate interviewing skills know what questions are appropriate to ask and how to obtain useful information. However, it is not uncommon for investigators to conduct interviews in inhumane ways. In fact, the purpose of interviews is to obtain accurate, reliable, and true information to reveal crimes so that they are worthy of being submitted to court (CTI, 2017).

One of the recommended interview methods is the cognitive interview technique which can improve the retrieval process (recall) which increases the quantity and quality of information by making the victim feel relaxed and cooperative (Fisher and Geiselman, 1992). This technique attempts to reduce the effect of suggestion on the basis that human memory is arranged in an overlapping, distorted, and fragmented manner with events that are stored (encoded). Fisher and Geiselman found that cognitive interview techniques produced 25-35% more results and were more accurate than standard police interview techniques or structured interviews. This interview technique is commonly used by police in the UK and US although it is not routinely carried out.

Fisher and Geiselman (1992) outlined seven stages of cognitive interview techniques. First, rapport (approach). At this stage, investigators approach the witness/victim so that they are not anxious, feel comfortable, and make them more concentrated. During the interview, pay attention to verbal and non-verbal communication, such as the use of polite and friendly words, voice intonation, speed of speech, and even facial expressions if you hear wrong information. Investigators also give witnesses/victims time to remember the incident and do not interrupt.

Also pay attention to eye contact, distance and sitting position, mention of the victim's name, and personality or mental factors.

Second, explain the purpose of the interview. Investigators should explain the purpose of the interview so that the witness/victim has time to remember the incident and prepare better. During the interview, the subject should be interviewed by one investigator. Based on research, subjects will not focus when interviewed by more than one person. Investigators must also motivate witnesses/victims to tell anything, even if they are unsure whether it is important or not. Or the subject only remembers part of it.

Third, report everything. Investigators can encourage witnesses/victims to tell any details of the incident even if they are considered unimportant. Fourth, probing. Investigators carry out probing (digging for more detailed information) on the descriptions and things conveyed by witnesses/victims. The goal is to gain confidence in relevant matters related to the events experienced. Fifth, recall the incident in a variety of ways, and recall the events in different orders. This means remembering events in various ways and in various time sequences. Usually witnesses/victims remember the sequence from beginning to end of the incident. After doing this, ask them to recall it in reverse. To test the veracity of the information, the investigator can tell that other people who were present at the time could see and hear from a different perspective. The victim can be asked to remember the incident from another person's perspective, for example from the perspective of another witness.

Sixth, summarizing. Investigators should summarize the information obtained from witnesses/victims and convey the summary results back to them. This is important so that miscommunication does not occur. Lastly, closing. The interview should be closed well so that it creates a positive impression of the victim. Slowly the investigator entered neutral conversation topics as in the initial stage. Give thanks as appreciation for the victim's efforts to concentrate and remember what happened. Provide a contact number that can be contacted if there is important information the victim wants to convey or if the victim needs information from investigators. At the end, investigators can provide information to the victim about the next stages.

4.4.6. Advocacy Support

During investigations and interviews, advocacy support is clearly valuable for those reporting sexual violence (Brooks and Burman, 2017). Fulfilment of victims' rights can be facilitated and initiated by the police unit which has the authority to handle the case from the time it is first reported. The presence of advocates is important in carrying out their work in order to advocate for victims' rights. Advocates often find intersectional factors complicate victims and cause them to feel unsafe when dealing with the courts. In carrying out their duties, advocates need to build partnerships with the community and other related institutions. It is important for them to better understand the duties of a victim advocate, which can lead to collaboration and better outcomes for victims (Rue, Rodriguez, dan Ortega, 2023).

Advocate support is important considering that imprisonment is not always an effective prevention or solution to cases of sexual violence. Although imprisoning the perpetrator represents justice for the state, it often does not represent justice for the victim. In fact, on the contrary, the investigation and trial process has the potential to make victims worse off than if they had never reported it at all (Carroll, 2023). When victims of sexual violence have legal counsel who informs, supports, and validates their experiences, victims are more likely to feel a sense of justice in the process they have gone through. Victims generally need recognition, dignity, voice, prevention, and connectedness following violence, seeking justice that is not often found in the criminal justice system.

Advocates can prevent secondary victimization that can occur through interrogation by police investigators (Carroll, 2023) and help victims regain a sense of autonomy, which has been taken away by crime. To provide effective support, it is carried out by trained advocates, with adequate knowledge, as well as compassion and empathy (Wedlock dan Tapley, 2016).

4.4.7. Mastery of Technology

Humanist policing can be developed through mastery of technology that significantly supports victims' rights. Technology is used as a means or instrument that facilitates victim services and speeds up the case handling process. Technology can also be used for data integration, monitoring, mapping, and communication platforms that connect victims with the police in real-time. Police human resource development includes the use of communication and information technology in every implementation of police duties and functions.

Certification of investigators specifically for women and children also needs to include training in mastering technology that will make policing performance effective and efficient. Mastery of technology is an important asset to face competition and anticipate legal changes in society. Education, training, and research in the field of police science and technology must be an inseparable part in relation to increasing the professionalism of digital human resources within the National Police (Faniyah dan Maulana, 2023).

4.4.8. Strategic Partnerships

The success of victim-oriented humanistic policing does not only depend on the management and resources of the police institution when handling cases of sexual violence against women and children. The success of policing is also helped by the possible involvement of strategic partners in facilitating and integrating police work. Like a symbiotic mutualism, the presence of external resources really helps facilitate policing services from upstream to downstream. Partners can be the Witness and Victim Protection Agency, Ministry of Women Empowerment and Child Protection, Ministry of Social Affairs, the Women and Children Services Unit, hospitals, professional staff, and local government.

This collaboration of resources not only aims to provide access to health and social care services, but can also include combined budgets. So far, the budget for financing victims is still scattered among each institution. The development of strategic partnerships in the future could be encouraged for cost collaboration (Dickinson and Neal, 2011). This is important considering the budget limitations of each supporting institution and the risk of ongoing funding for victims of serious crimes. As in New Zealand, the police have succeeded in developing supporting sectors such as finance, providing training, and developing networks between staff, so that handling victims does not depend on police decisions. (Rowe & Macauley, 2019).

In line with the trend of community-based policing, partnerships can be established between the police and the community (Paterson & Williams, 2018, p. 87). Community policing has become the model of choice for democratic police agencies seeking to increase legitimacy and build public trust, although there remains significant criticism regarding the extent to which this model is successful. However, as community participation increases, community involvement is important considering they are objects of law and providers of information as well as places where crimes occur. It is hoped that community participation can help push the direction of policing that is more humane and pro-victim.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion above, several conclusions can be drawn. First, the forms of service for victims of sexual violence crimes in the police in Indonesia are generally still not optimal even though progress has been made. There are still many victims' rights that are not adequately served and facilitated. During the investigation process, victims tend to experience intimidation, discrimination, and efforts to "save" the perpetrator through restorative justice (RJ) mechanisms. There are also cases where victims provide incentives to investigators so that their cases are handled quickly. The police also tend to work based on procedural logic so they do not necessarily believe the victim, and only rely on supporting evidence which can be difficult to obtain.

In line with the dynamics of law and digital activism, Indonesia National Police continues to transform by improving its organizational culture and special competencies. There are methods to improve human resources

and competencies through integrated education and training, seminars, workshops, FGDs, and similar activities. However, in general the availability of resources in the form of human resources for special investigators, infrastructure, and budget is inadequate and is still concentrated in certain areas, such as DKI Jakarta. In many regions, the availability of resources is still minimal so many cases are delegated to the center. Not to mention, there is not much interest in young police officers to become special investigators for women and children compared to detective investigators.

Changes in policing culture due to digital activism have made the police more responsive by providing online services. This service provides access for victims to report, consult and ask for help; as well as educating and empowering the public regarding knowledge about news, information, education, vocational skills, technology, etc. However, for legal facts, the police still rely on physical reports at the police station, including picking up victims if they do not report them.

Second, the forms of service for victims of sexual violence crimes in Japan are very democratic. The Japanese police adhere to four main principles, namely assisting, listening, explaining, and protecting. Assistance is provided from the time the victim experiences the incident until taking the victim home for free. Apart from assistance, the police will also always listen to victims' complaints and are willing to answer to find a solution to the case. The police will also explain the progress of the case until the trial as well as provide explanation assistance for the victim's relatives. Another principle is to protect victims through intense communication via electronic mail.

The Japanese police consider sexual violent crimes to be a "huge loss to the country". This assessment is based on Japan's promise to provide happiness for every citizen, including sexual happiness and long-term livelihood support. The police will try to position themselves as victims. Usually, the Japanese police involve supervisory investigators as instructors for sexual violent crime investigations. The investigation process was also carried out by National Police agents specifically for women as an effort to prevent the victim's mental burden. Victims of criminal acts receive three main rights, namely victim insurance, medical insurance, and life insurance. Fulfilling this right is the responsibility of the police to protect the security, safety, and happiness of citizens. Uniquely, the Japanese police have special officers to handle cases that occur on trains and have a *Chiba's Taiwa no Kai* approach, namely meetings between victims and perpetrators facilitated by independent associations.

Third, forms of service for victims of sexual violence crimes in New Zealand are carried out by placing victims as a priority and avoiding discrimination. The determination of victims' rights in New Zealand Police receives adequate attention, which includes the rights to receive assistance, protection, and support for recovery from prolonged trauma. New Zealand Police has the main vision of making New Zealand the safest and most comfortable country for the people. Since 2018, KSB has been committed to opening its eyes wide to victims. For this reason, KSB's policing style is very different from many other countries. New Zealand Police' policing focus emphasizes communication and adheres to the teaching that every interaction is an opportunity to prevent crime. This principle influences the way police officers respond and encourages the community to work together to achieve more positive results in the long term.

Apart from the community, New Zealand Police also forms partnerships with social workers and NGOs or what is called the Multi-Agency Center (MAC) which is basically a center for victims of child abuse or adult sexual violence. New Zealand Police also includes local Māori culture in solving crime cases. This partnership allows wider support for victims, where they talk not only about the victim, but also regarding family losses, care, especially the victim's traumatic condition.

As technology develops, New Zealand Police utilizes organizational resources through the use of national intelligence applications called NEAR and Checkpoint, which function as health references, evaluations, crime maps, and databases.

Fourth, there are similarities as well as significant differences between the service models for victims of sexual violence crimes in Indonesia and those in Japan and New Zealand. If Indonesia has not given priority to

fulfilling victims' basic rights, both countries are more progressive in providing services to fulfil victims' rights. The police in both countries operate based on democratic rules and legal principles.

Finally, the theoretical model of victims-oriented humanistic policing by the Indonesian police can be approached through five strategic approaches, namely continuous assisting, practical interview skills, advocacy, use of technology, and strategic partnerships. These five theoretical concepts emphasize a transformational focus for law enforcers to prevent secondary victimization when dealing with victims. Assistance is provided continuously from the time the case is reported until the victim returns home safely. During an investigation, interviewing skills are needed so that victims are not intimidated or discriminated against so that legal truth and justice can be achieved. Meanwhile, advocacy support is needed so that victims do not feel alone, and their rights can be fought for. The police must also have competence in mastering technology that will facilitate services for victims. In carrying out all this, the police should partner with external institutions and the community to ensure that services for victims are carried out adequately from start to finish.

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